

PROPOSED STUDY SUMMARY	
Title	Role of the natural and anthropogenic aerosols in the Mediterranean region: past climate variability and future climate sensitivity
Abstract <i>(no more than 500 words and detailing how this proposal addressing the FPS criteria.)</i>	<p>Aerosols strongly affect the Mediterranean basin located at the crossroads of air masses carrying both natural and anthropogenic particles making the basin an ideal testbed for aerosol effects on climate. The aerosols have strong effects on the regional climate fluctuations from daily to multi-decadal scales due to their direct, semi-direct and indirect effects on radiation, atmospheric circulation and cloud cover. Aerosols also represent one of the main sources of uncertainty in past climate change attribution and future climate change projections at global and regional scales. Due to their relatively short life-time, aerosols influencing the Mediterranean area are mostly produced in nearby regions and therefore they constitute a regional climate forcing of regional origin. In addition, the aerosols show a high spatio-temporal variability and are influenced by numerous fine-scale processes.. The use of high-resolution RCMs therefore fits well to address the four main scientific questions of the proposed FPS:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Can we fully characterize the Mediterranean aerosol past variability and future evolution at climate scales ? in particular using RCMs. (2) Can we understand the role of the Mediterranean aerosols on the past regional climate variability ? including issues related to regional climate change attribution and aerosols representation in climate models (GCM, RCM). (3) Can we determine the role of regionally-born aerosols in the Mediterranean future climate sensitivity ? in particular using RCMs as complementary approach to GCMs. (4) What is the aerosol role in shaping the Mediterranean extreme events ? (e.g. heat waves, heavy precipitation events) <p>The proposed FPS will be facilitated by recent observation efforts such as the ChArMEx programme, long-term multi-variable super-sites, availability of new homogenized datasets for AOD and surface shortwave and longwave radiations from in-situ coordinated networks (AERONET, GEBA, BRSN) and climate-aware satellite initiatives (ESA-CCI).</p>

	<p>The representation of aerosols and their effects in RCMs is still very crude and uncertain and a multi-model approach is therefore requested to bring robust answers to the scientific questions CORDEX then constitutes an adequate framework to propose scientifically-based and well-coordinated simulation protocols involving RCMs with various aerosol representations</p> <p>The proposed FPS targets in particular a better understanding of solar radiation variability and future changes. This is required to anticipate potential energy production or to understand the level of production of existing sites. The FPS may therefore leads to new and innovative climate services for energy producers over the Euro-Mediterranean area. Another outcomes of the FPS concerns the marine biogeochemistry of the oligotrophic Mediterranean Sea ecosystem as particles constitute one of the main sources of regional nutrients.</p> <p>Besides, this FPS will contribute to several WCRP Grand Challenges, to the CORDEX Challenge about the coupled regional climate models and to the climate modelling activities of the Mediterranean regional programmes of Gewex (HyMeX) and CLIVAR (Med-CLIVAR).</p>
Expected study duration	5 years (2016-2020)

LEAD INVESTIGATOR DETAILS	
Name	(i) Fabien Solmon (ii) Marc Mallet
Affiliation	(i) The Abdus Salam International Center for Theoretical Physics (ICTP) (ii) Laboratoire d'Aérodologie (LA / CNRS)
Email address	solmon@ictp.it marc.mallet@aero.obs-mip.fr
Address	(i) Strada Costiera 11, Trieste, Italy (ii) OMP, 14 avenue edouard Belin, Toulouse, France.

PARTICIPATING PARTNERS

Copy and paste partner section as required for further partners

Partner 1	Name	Pierre Nabat
	Affiliation	Météo-France / Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques
	Email address	pierre.nabat@meteo.fr
	Address	42 avenue Coriolis, 31057 Toulouse cedex, France
Partner 2	Name	Enrique Sanchez
	Affiliation	University of Castilla-La Mancha
	Email address	e.sanchez@uclm.es
	Address	Av. Carlos III s/n, 45071, Toledo, Spain
Partner 3	Name	Sylvain Mailler
	Affiliation	Institut Pierre Simon Laplace
	Email address	sylvain.mailler@lmd.polytechnique.fr
	Address	Ecole Polytechnique, 91 128 Palaiseau Cedex, France
Partner 4	Name	Eleni Katragkou]
	Affiliation	Department of Meteorology and Climatology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
	Email address	katragou@auth.gr
	Address	University Campus, 54124, Thessaloniki, Greece
Partner 5	Name	Vassiliki Kotroni
	Affiliation	National Observatory of Athens, Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development
	Email address	kotroni@noa.gr
	Address	I. Metaxa & V. Pavlou, P. Penteli, 15236, Athens, Greece
Partner 6	Name	Bodo Ahrens
	Affiliation	Goethe University Frankfurt am Main
	Email address	Bodo.Ahrens@iau.uni-frankfurt.de
	Address	Altenhoefer Allee 1, 60438 Frankfurt am Main

Partner 7	Name	Alessandro Dell'Aquila
	Affiliation	ENEA, Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development; Climate & Impact Modeling Laboratory
	Email address	alessandro.dellaquila@enea.it
	Address	Bldg C59, Room 10A Sp. 118 CR Casaccia, Via Anguillarese, 301 00123 Santa Maria di Galeria - Rome- ITALY
Partner 8	Name	Tony C. Landi
	Affiliation	ISAC - Istituto di Scienze dell'Atmosfera e del Clima, CNR - Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
	Email address	t.landi@isac.cnr.it
	Address	Via Gobetti 101, 40129 Bologna, Italia.
Partner 9	Name	Piero Lionello
	Affiliation	Univ. del Salento - and CMCC
	Email address	piero.lionello@unisalento.it
	Address	via per Monteroni, n.165, plesso M, 73100 Lecce, Italy
Partner 10	Name	Levent kurnaz
	Affiliation	Bogazici University Physics Department
	Email address	mlkurnaz@gmail.com
	Address	34342 Bebek / Istanbul; TURKEY North Campus, KB Building Floor 3-4

PROPOSAL

Maximum of 750 words for this section with all headings to be addressed

<p>Objectives</p>	<p>Numerous and various aerosols affect the Mediterranean basin (Lelieveld et al., 2002), located at the crossroads of air masses carrying both natural (desertic particles, sea-salt, volcanic ashes) and anthropogenic (black carbon, sulphate) particles. Because of their microphysical and optical properties, these aerosols can have strong direct effects on the regional radiative budget (Bergamo et al., 2008) and a large range of semi-direct and indirect effects on clouds. They do impact regional climate fluctuations from daily to multi-decadal scales (Nabat et al. 2014, 2015ab), as well as Mediterranean Seaecosystems (Guieu et al., 2010). Aerosols also constitute one of the main sources of uncertainty in past climate change attribution and future climate change projections at global and regional scales (IPCC-AR5) and are not well represented in current RCMs. Due to their relatively short life-time, aerosols influencing the Mediterranean area are mostly produced in nearby regions and therefore constitute a regional climate forcing of regional origin, strongly influenced by synoptic circulation (Flaounas et al. 2015) as well as by small-scale processes (Nabat et al. 2012).</p> <p>The main objectives of the FPS are to fully characterize the Mediterranean aerosol variability at climate scale and to understand their impacts on the Mediterranean past regional climate variability and future climate sensitivity.</p>
<p>Relevance to CORDEX vision</p>	<p>To fulfil these objectives, high-resolution RCMs have the capacity to (1) complement GCM studies to disentangle the regional climate influence of aerosols (2) add value to lower resolution climate models (GCMs) due to a better representation of the various aerosol life cycle phases and (3) allow a better assessment of the role of the aerosols in the regional climate projections. The representation of aerosols in RCMs is still uncertain and a multi-model approach within the established CORDEX framework is suitable to bring robust answers to the scientific questions. Coordination of the proposed Med-CORDEX-originated FPS with similar CORDEX initiatives will be foreseen and will contribute to the CORDEX challenges on coupled regional climate models.</p>

<p>Science aims</p>	<p>The proposed FPS targets four main scientific questions:</p> <p>(1) Can we fully characterize the Mediterranean aerosol past variability and future evolution at climate scales ? in particular using RCMs.</p> <p>(2) Can we understand the role of the Mediterranean aerosols on the past regional climate variability ? including issues related to regional climate change attribution and aerosols representation in climate models (GCM, RCM).</p> <p>(3) Can we determine the role of regionally-born aerosols in the Mediterranean future climate sensitivity ? in particular using RCMs as complementary approach to GCMs.</p> <p>(4) What is the aerosol role in shaping the Mediterranean extreme events ? (e.g. heat waves, heavy precipitation events)</p>
<p>Expected impact</p> <p><i>(e.g scientific, end user, policy)</i></p>	<p>Innovative scientific results in regional climate science</p> <p>A better understanding of the past Mediterranean regional climate variability.</p> <p>A better representation of aerosols radiative forcing and cloud processes in RCMs- Better assessment of the future evolution of the regional climate (including surface shortwave radiation, cloud cover), solar energy production capacity, air quality, and marine biogeochemistry in the Mediterranean.</p> <p>Contribution to Euro-Mediterranean climate services.</p> <p>Added-value assessment of coupled RCMs with respect to Atmosphere-RCMs</p> <p>Contribution to WCRP Grand Challenges (Understanding and Predicting Weather ; Climate Extremes, Changes in Water availability)</p>
<p>Project timeline</p> <p><i>Detail the key milestones and responsibilities throughout project duration</i></p>	<p>Two complementary, scientifically-based and well-coordinated protocols using RCMs are proposed:</p> <p><u>Protocol1: External aerosol forcing</u></p> <p>Sensitivity RCM experiments using external aerosol forcings (direct and indirect effects) will be carried out in evaluation and scenario mode. Three configurations will be tested with imposed climatologies to disentangle the role of the aerosol in the Mediterranean: No aerosol, constant aerosol, time-varying aerosols.</p>

	<p><u>Protocol2 : Interactive aerosol</u></p> <p>Fully interactive aerosol-climate RCMs will be used on an extended Med-CORDEX domain including all the source regions for a hierarchy of runs: (1) 3-month case study (typically summer 2013), (2) reanalysis-driven evaluation runs (minimum 2000-2013, better 1979-2013), (3) RCP8.5 projections (minimum two 20-year time slices, better 1950-2050, CMIP5 LBCs)</p> <p><u>Milestones:</u></p> <p>Finalize FPS partner list for each protocol (M3)</p> <p>Finalize protocol definition (common aerosol dataset, extended domain, case study, common diagnostics) (M6)</p> <p>Launch protocol2 case study simulations and protocol1 runs (M12)</p> <p>Launch protocol2 evaluation simulations (M24)</p> <p>Launch protocol2 scenario simulations (M36)</p> <p>FPS reference article with all partners and opening of a dedicated special issue (M48)</p> <p>Availability of model documentation and CMOR simulation outputs ESGF (M60)</p> <p>The FPS Lead Investigators will ensure the communication between FPS partners (minimum 1 meeting per year), monitor FPS progression, report to Med-CORDEX steering committee and CORDEX SAT.</p>
--	--

<p style="text-align: center;">CRITERIA ADDRESSED</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>How does your proposal address the following criteria (maximum 200 words per criteria)</i></p>	
<p>1. Targeting fine scale processes and clear scientific questions of interest</p>	<p>The scientific questions are justified and detailed above.</p> <p>Concerning the fine scale processes, the aerosol life cycle depends to numerous small-scale processes related to the emission, transport and deposition. High-resolution RCMs will notably improve their representation, for example for emission, through a better description of source geographical gradients, surface wind and temperatures and through an improved representation of meso-scale systems/features impacting aerosol and pollution transport and impacts (e.g. sea-breeze, marine boundary layer, valley inversions, convective emissions,</p>

	<p>transport and scavenging, deposition on glaciers/snow covers).</p> <p>In addition, the climatic response to aerosol perturbation forcing occurs through scales varying from local to global. The RCM approach will bring particular added values through a better representation of potentially strong gradients of the radiative forcing triggering or not the regional scale dynamical response and through an improved representation of regional cloud covers and types and their interactions with specific aerosol types.</p> <p>Finally, specific assessments of the climatic impact and significance of different kind of aerosol forcings (direct LW and SW, semi-directs and indirects) is potentially possible through this FPS.</p>
<p>2. Use of observational data including not only meteorological but also derived data (e.g. soil moisture, streamflow etc.)</p>	<p>The proposed FPS will be facilitated by recent observation efforts such as the ChArMEx programme, long-term multi-variable super-sites, availability of new homogenized datasets for AOD and surface shortwave and longwave radiations from in-situ coordinated networks (AERONET, GEBA, BRSN) and climate-aware satellite initiatives (ESA-CCI). In particular, the ChArMEx programme dedicated to the study of the Chemistry and Aerosols in the Mediterranean Experiment will provide datasets from intensive field campaigns performed during the summers 2012 and 2013 as well as from long-term observation networks allowing the models evaluation for the aerosol representation. This includes (1) measurements during the field campaign at different surface stations and onboard two aircrafts; (2) chemical, physical and optical properties of aerosols, vertical profiles at different surface stations and (3) dry and wet aerosol deposition network at different stations over the Mediterranean. In addition, long-term super-sites (SIRTA, Lampedusa, Corsica) gathering multi-variables measurements and networks of homogenized AOD and surface shortwave and longwave radiation are becoming available to evaluate the aerosol-cloud and aerosol-radiation interactions. This makes the proposed FPS very timely.</p>
<p>3. End-to-end perspective and potential to support demonstrated local/regional needs</p>	<p>Aerosols have been shown to strongly influence shortwave radiation at the surface, which is important for planning purposes of solar energy power plants. A good knowledge of the statistics of the surface downward shortwave radiation (direct and diffuse) is thus required to anticipate potential energy production for new site planning or to understand the level of production of existing sites. The findings of the proposed FPS may then evolve in new and innovative operational climate services dedicated to the energy producers for the Euro-</p>

	<p>Mediterranean region in relation with Copernicus C3S.</p> <p>In terms of air quality, dust and other natural aerosols can contribute to a significant fraction of Particulate Matter 10 (PM10) background. The variability of this background and its possible future evolution shall be characterized, for example for a better assessment of anthropogenic PM emissions reduction strategies. Through particle-gas phase interactions, aerosols can also impact the regional atmospheric chemistry and pollutant like ozone. In the future, this may contribute to Euro-Mediterranean climate services on air-quality.</p> <p>Marine and terrestrial biogeochemistry is also impacted by aerosols insofar as dust particles constitute one of the main sources of nutrients and can influence the functioning of the Mediterranean Sea oligotrophic ecosystem with implication for marine biodiversity and conservation planning.</p>
<p>4. Applicant group</p>	<p>Med-CORDEX (including the HyMeX and Charmex regional climate modelling communities).</p> <p>This includes currently 12 partners using at least 6 different RCMs: RegCM (various configurations), ALADIN-Climate, PROMES, WRF (various configurations), COSMO-CLM, LMDZ.</p>

SUGGESTIONS FOR POTENTIAL REVIEWERS		
<p>Reviewer 1</p>	<p>Name</p>	<p>Ina Tegen</p>
	<p>Position</p>	<p>Professor</p>
	<p>Affiliation</p>	<p>Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research Permoserstraße 15 04318 Leipzig ina.tegen@tropos.de</p>
	<p>Expertise</p>	<p>Aerosol modeling, observations and impacts, Saharan dust cycle.</p>
<p>Reviewer 2</p>	<p>Name</p>	<p>Allison Steiner</p>
	<p>Position</p>	<p>Professor</p>
	<p>Affiliation</p>	<p>Department of Climate and Space Sciences and Engineering University of Michigan</p>

		Space Research Building 2455 Hayward St. Ann Arbor, MI 48109-2143 alsteiner@umich.edu
	Expertise	Regional climate modeling, aerosol and atmospheric chemistry

References

Bergamo, A., Tafuro, A. M., Kinne, S., De Tomasi, F., and Perrone, M. R.: Monthly-averaged anthropogenic aerosol direct radiative forcing over the Mediterranean based on AERONET aerosol properties, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 8, 6995–7014, doi:10.5194/acp-8-6995-2008, 2008.

Flaounas, E., Kotroni, V., Lagouvardos, K., Kazadzis, S., Gkikas, A. and Hatzianastassiou, N. (2015), Cyclone contribution to dust transport over the Mediterranean region. *Atmosph. Sci. Lett.*, 16: 473–478. doi: 10.1002/asl.584

Guieu, C., Dulac, F., Desboeufs, K., Wagener, T., Pulido-Villena, E., Grisoni, J.-M., Louis, F., Ridame, C., Blain, S., Brunet, C., Bon Nguyen, E., Tran, S., Labiadh, M., and Dominici, J.-M.: Large clean mesocosms and simulated dust deposition: a new methodology to investigate responses of marine oligotrophic ecosystems to atmospheric inputs, *Biogeosciences*, 7, 2765–2784, doi:10.5194/bg-7-2765-2010, 2010.

IPCC, 2013: Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G. - K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1535 pp, doi:10.1017/CBO9781107415324.

Lelieveld, J., Berresheim, H., Borrmann, S., Crutzen, P. J., Dentener, F. J., Fischer, H., Feichter, J., Flatau, P. J., Heland, J., Holzinger, R., Kormann, R., Lawrence, M. G., Levin, Z., Markowicz, K. M., Mihalopoulos, N., Minikin, A., Ramanathan, V., de Reus, M., Roelofs, G. J., Scheeren, H. A., Sciare, J., Schlager, H., Schultz, M., Siegmund, P., Steil, B., Stephanou, E. G., Stier, P., Traub, M., Warneke, C., Williams, J., and Ziereis, H.: Global air pollution crossroads over the Mediterranean, *Science*, 298, 794–799, doi:10.1126/science.1075457, 2002.

Nabat, P., Solmon, F., Mallet, M., Kok, J. F., and Somot, S (2012): Dust emission size distribution impact on aerosol budget and radiative forcing over the Mediterranean region: a regional climate model approach, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 12, 10545-10567, doi:10.5194/acp-12-10545-2012, 2012.

Nabat, P., Somot, S., Mallet, M., Sanchez-Lorenzo, A., and Wild, M.: Contribution of anthropogenic sulfate aerosols to the changing Euro-Mediterranean climate since 1980, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 41, 5605–5611, doi:10.1002/2014GL060798, 2014.

Nabat, P., Somot, S., Mallet, M., Sevault, F., Chiacchio, M, and Wild, M.: Direct and semi-direct aerosol radiative effect on the Mediterranean climate variability using a coupled regional climate system model, *Clim. Dynam.*, 44, 1127–1155, doi:10.1007/s00382-014-2205-6, 2015a.

Nabat, P., Somot, S., Mallet, M., Michou, M., Sevault, F., Driouech, F., Meloni, D., di Sarra, A., Di Biagio, C., Formenti, P., Sicard, M., Léon, J.-F., and Bouin, M.-N.: Dust aerosol radiative effects during

summer 2012 simulated with a coupled regional aerosol–atmosphere–ocean model over the Mediterranean, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 15, 3303–3326, doi: 10.5194/acp-15-3303-2015, 2015b.